

Optical Wireless in Support of a Computing-Communication Continuum for Connected Mobility

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Abstract: The need to exchange vast amounts of data among road-side users and edge computing puts optical wireless access into the focus of 6G. This contribution highlights two optical wireless modes for the far-access and fronthaul segment, building on low-cost transceivers for joint communication and lighting and robust fibre-in-the-air connectivity, respectively. Towards these directions, we discuss (i) the capability of light emitting diodes to establish Gb/s visible-light communication links using simple on-off keying for a format-transparent relay of Ethernet, and (ii) alignment-tolerant coupling between single-mode fibre cores by means of optical beamforming, which further mitigates turbulence in free-space links that extend fibre-grade capacity to isolated fibre networks through a Fi-Wi-Fi bridge.

I. INTRODUCTION

An attractive way to face congestion of the available electro-magnetic spectrum while suppressing interference at the same time is to off-load data transmission to the optical domain. In the context of connected mobility, such a strategy requires the employment of electro-optic signal converters. An economically viable way to do so is to re-use front- and rear-lighting assets as optical data transmitters for vehicular-to-vehicular (V2V) visible-light communication (VLC). At the same time, a sufficiently high communication bandwidth needs to be provisioned between the far-access street segment and computational resources at the edge. Towards this goal, fibre scarcity might call for optical wireless connectivity that offers fibre-grade capacity to sustain a seamless communication-computation continuum. This infrastructure-to-infrastructure (I2I) mode for free-space optical (FSO) communication ideally provides a transparent pipe between two single-mode fibre (SMF) cores. This paper discusses optical wireless solutions supporting such V2V and I2I connectivity.

Fig. 1. (a) Bandwidth extension for high-flux LED emitters. (b) LiDAR point-cloud relay over out-door VLC link.

II. VLC THROUGH RE-USE OF LED-BASED LIGHTING

Optical wireless communication between two electro-optic converters can build on a variety of optical sources emitting coherent and incoherent light. In the 6G-EWOC project, we primarily focus on simple, cost-effective and incoherent light emitters such as light emitting diodes (LED) that are commonly found in lighting. Even though micro-LEDs have been demonstrated with high electro-optic bandwidths exceeding 1 GHz [1], the larger active die sizes and unfavourable circuit characteristics of high-flux LEDs render these high-power emitters as unsuitable for fast electro-optic modulation. Typical electro-optic 3-dB bandwidths are 22 and 5 MHz for LEDs offering a flux of 18 and 340 lm, respectively [2-5]. In order to support low-latency Ethernet connectivity over a V2V link, three conditions need to be met, including (i) an end-to-end response suitable for on-off keying (OOK) at Ethernet line rates, (ii) a line of sight between VLC transmitter and receiver, and (iii) a transmission performance that supports a sufficiently high optical budget for the V2V VLC link.

Fig. 1(a) proves that the first condition can be met when adopting simple analogue frequency-response equalization in the driver feed path of the LED, without the need for digital signal processing. This pre-emphasis by 13.5 (●) and 28 dB (▼) for a LED with a flux of 20 lm enables a modulation bandwidth of up to 77 and 746 MHz, which is sufficient large for direct OOK transmission at 100 Mb/s and 1 Gb/s, respectively. To prove this point, Fig. 1(b) presents the fusion of two point clouds acquired by light-based ranging and detection (LiDAR) technology, whereas the data encircling RSU1 has been transmitted over a 100M Ethernet-over-VLC connection over a distance of 102 m towards RSU2 [5]. No sector was lost during point-cloud transmission. This shows that simple LED emitters, in combination with 2" collimation optics and avalanche photodetectors (APD), can cater for the relay of raw road-side data for local data fusion – without the need for prior data compression. An expansion of the supported field-of-view would require alignment-tolerant receivers [6].

Fig. 2. (a) Fi-Wi-Fi bridge configuration and focal plane of the beamformer. (b) FSO coupling between two SMF cores. (c) Mitigation of optical turbulence.

III. FREE-SPACE OPTICAL FI-WI-FI BRIDGE

The collection of vast road-side data for subsequent processing in edge compute datacentres requires the provisioning of fibre-grade capacities. FSO can contribute such in fibre-scarce environments, provided that fibre continuity can be guaranteed. This, however, necessitates low-loss coupling between SMF cores – even in presence of poor atmospheric conditions and turbulence, which both contribute to signal fading at a slow and fast timescale, respectively.

Optical beamforming can be adopted to address these challenges when implementing fibre-in-the-air optical wireless connectivity. In the 6G-EWOC project, we build on a focal plane array (FPA) beamformer native to fibre-optic technology: It leverages on a photonic lantern with up to 91 hexagonally packed cores that resemble the antenna elements at the focal plane. A typical FSO configuration involving such FPAs in a Fi-Wi-Fi bridge is shown in Fig. 2(a). Fine beam steering for this point-to-point FSO link between two ITU-T G.652B compatible SMF cores is accomplished through either space- or wavelength-switching, as explained in detail in [7]. By altering the antenna element at the transmit- and receive-side FSO terminal, the offset from the lens centre of the FPA beamformers leads to a deflection in beam emission. By choosing a small step size in steering angle by FPA design, the optical coupling between two FPA beamformers can be optimized – even though the initial setup of FSO terminals was merely based on simple pointing. The established optical pipe between two SMF cores enables a transparent and alignment-tolerant interconnect between two fibre networks, without re-translating the signals from the optical to the electrical domain.

An example for Fi-Wi-Fi coupling over a 63-m out-door link with 2" lens optics is presented in Fig. 2(b). The received optical power peaks at -13.5 dBm for carrier-grade launch levels, with 92 more optical antenna element pairs yielding an optical power within a 6-dB margin from this maximum. The accomplished coupling suits APD-based data reception. Alternatively, simple optical re-amplification can be adopted to extend the reach and/or budget of optical networks over the Fi-Wi-Fi bridge. Moreover, optical channel sounding can be gracefully implemented in order to determine the optimal beamformer settings. As demonstrated in [7], simultaneous sounding can be accomplished by dedicating a second waveband, which mirrors the coupling profile of Fig. 2(b) in this parallel spectral region – provided that cyclic wavelength routing is employed at the receiver-side FPA beamformer. The remote setting of the receiver-side antenna element through simple wavelength choice enables centralized beamforming according to the acquired spectral sounding profile.

On top of this, the utilized FPA configuration allows for an effective mitigation of turbulence when expanding communication between single antenna elements at each side of the FSO link to a multi-element diversity scheme [8]. This is accomplished by

implementing data transmission on a set of wavelengths rather than on a single wavelength. Optical turbulence then causes beam wander and spread to multiple receive-side antenna elements. The faded signal at the originally set antenna element can then be recovered through simple beam combining around multiple (neighbouring) elements. Our experimental findings indicate that a set of 4 (7) wavelengths provide a diversity gain of 4.6 (5.5) dB in optical power, yielding again an open eye, as evidenced in Fig. 2(c).

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